

Key Performance Indicators in Humanitarian Logistics: a Systematic Literature Review 2010-2020

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Abstract: This article analyzes the operational performance measurement in humanitarian logistics (HL). To this end, a systematic literature review (SLR) was performed aiming to present general information about the context of performance measurement in HL, based on relevant studies on the subject. Thus, 55 articles published from 2010 to 2020 were examined to answer three research questions (RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3). The results underline an increasing trend of the number of publications related to the performance measurement in HL, probably led by the growing pressure for humanitarian organizations (HO) to deliver increasingly efficient and effective operations. The gaps and, consequently, the research opportunities, identified by the analysis of the articles, can guide the planning and implementation of the performance measurement of HL in different situations, bringing benefits to both users and suppliers in this chain.

Keywords: Humanitarian supply chain, measurement, performance measure.

Introduction

Humanitarian logistics (HL) aims to assist people suffering the effects of a disaster with essential resources, which are often provided by non-governmental organizations (NGOs) or private sector donors [1-2].

Measuring the humanitarian supply chain (HSC) performance has become necessary and important for humanitarian organizations (HO) to obtain and retain public and private donors to finance their operations, who demand more and more transparency and accountability, and are also becoming less and less tolerant of inefficiencies [3-4].

In general, performance measurement can be defined as the process of analyzing and quantifying information related to the efficiency and effectiveness of an action [5, 24, 34]. However, research shows that 55% of humanitarian organizations neither monitor nor report any indicators for measuring performance, 25% use only a few indicators and only 20% measure performance consistently [5].

Therefore, this research aimed to conduct a systematic literature review (SLR) of articles published in the topic of Humanitarian Logistics (HL) from 2010 to 2020, to answer the following research questions:

- ✓ *RQ1: What does recent literature report on utilization and discovery to the practice of humanitarian logistics?*
- ✓ *RQ2: What are the main attributes and indicators for performance measurement that humanitarian logistics researchers employ/report in their studies?*
- ✓ *RQ3: What are the main research gaps in the literature observed regarding performance indicators in humanitarian logistics?*

The SLR aims to gather empirical evidence that fits predefined eligibility criteria to answer research questions [6]. By answering these questions, a greater understanding of HL practices and a guide of possible aspects to be explored on the subject are obtained. The current global scenario caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, which COVID-19 has rapidly turned into an unprecedented health, economic and geopolitical crisis, reinforces the importance of efficient and effective humanitarian logistics [7]. Therefore, studies aimed at understanding the specific characteristics of this process, such as this study, are essential for its improvement.

Methods

This work was based on the methodology proposed by [8], as shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1. SLR methodology steps.
 Source: Adapted from [8].

Step 1 begins with defining the need for SLR, linked to well-formulated research questions. Steps 2 and 3 are included in the research protocol. A well-formulated protocol is an essential component of a systematic review, as it guides the course of the entire process and differentiates it from other types of reviews [9]. This work followed the protocol summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Research protocol

Procedure	Description
Objective	Answer to RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3.
Key words	Humanitarian Logistics/ Humanitarian Supply Chain Performance Measure/ Performance Measuring/ Performance Measurement
Boolean operator	AND/OR
String	Title = (("humanitarian logistics" OR "humanitarian supply chain") AND performance AND (measure OR measuring OR measurement)) OR Abstract = (("humanitarian logistics" OR "humanitarian supply chain") AND performance AND (measure OR measuring OR measurement)) OR Key words = (("humanitarian logistics" OR "humanitarian supply chain") AND performance AND (measure OR measuring OR measurement)).
Databases	Web of Science, Scopus and Science Direct.
Period	From 2010 to 2020
Inclusion criteria	Complete articles from international journals, peer-reviewed and written in English
Exclusion criteria	Articles that only cite the key words but do not directly relate humanitarian logistics or supply chain to performance measurement

Step 4 is nothing more than the implementation of the research mechanisms established by the previous steps, in order to select only studies relevant to the topic. A total of 88 articles returned, 26 of which were duplicate, leaving 62 articles. After careful reading, considering the exclusion criteria, 55 articles were selected.

Step 5 consists of analyzing the selected papers. The goal of this step is to break down individual studies into parts, describe how each one relates to the other and, at the same time, make associations between the identified parts [10]. Finally, the results are presented, as per the next section.

Results and Discussion

Analyzing the articles, it was observed that recently the performance measurement in the context of HL has received greater attention from researchers, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Number of articles per year

This trend of increasing studies can be explained the fact that humanitarian operations are under constant pressure to improve their efficiency and effectiveness [11], making it essential to manage and measure the performance of such operations for this [5].

Regarding the types of studies, the publications were classified into four categories, which were:

1. Case study: studies that used one or more Humanitarian Organizations (HO), or real emergency situations, as an object to apply the systems and methodologies developed by the researchers.
2. Exploratory study: studies whose function is to fill existing gaps, provide more information and subsidies that facilitate applications and future studies.
3. Study based on expert opinions: studies that used data collected through consulting with experts in the areas and/or sectors studied.

4. Simulation: use of pre-existing real data and/or simulated networks to apply systems and methodologies developed by the researchers.

Based on this classification, the distribution of articles can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Distribution of publications by type of study

It can be seen that 38.7% of the publications are studies that involve simulation, even using data from previous case studies. Critical situations involving Humanitarian Logistics demand large-scale problem solving, which requires effective and near-optimal solutions quickly. In this way, simulations, based on pre-existing data, allow testing the operational validity of the created model, its usefulness, as well as its limitations, thus supporting more objective and effective practical operations [4, 12-14].

As for the general objectives of the studied articles, different types of objectives were identified regarding performance evaluations in Humanitarian Logistics (HL), in which each one of them deals with particularities that impact the final performance of the realization of HL. In order to facilitate understanding, based on [15], the following classification of such objectives was developed in this study:

- ✓ **Measurement:** Refers to articles that developed or applied methodologies for measuring aspects of HL, such as: the effectiveness and efficiency of HL chains in relation to various metrics found in the literature, such as availability of resources, cost of operation, priority, delivery time and accuracy, quality of items and so on.
- ✓ **Planning:** Refers to articles that developed/applied models that contribute to the planning of HL operations and, consequently, to the improvement of its performance, such as: Decision Support System, optimization of resource allocation and networks, optimization of distribution, identification of supply partners, etc.

- ✓ **Research support:** Refers to articles that, through an exploratory study, focused on organizing the literature, identifying and/or categorizing performance indicators, and evaluating their usefulness in the face of HL, to support future research.

Table 2 shows that Measurement and Planning are objective most discussed in the literature studied. Humanitarian Organizations need to obtain and retain public and private donors to finance their operations [4]. Thus, plan and measure performance of the humanitarian supply chain are steps of fundamental importance for an efficient management [16].

Table 2. Distribution of publications by type of objective

Objective	Author	Qty.
Measurement	2, 3, 11, 12, 16-35	24
Planning	4, 13-14, 36-55	24
Research support	1, 5, 56-60	7

Thus, based on the readings of the articles and, with the help of the analyses presented so far, it became possible to answer the research questions (Q1, Q2 and Q3), initially elaborated as objectives of the SLR.

Answer - RQ1

In a context of growing natural disasters, political and religious conflicts, the field of knowledge on Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management (HLSCM) attracts the attention of various stakeholders [58].

Events such as the terrorist attack of September 11, 2001, Hurricane Katrina in 2005, Cyclone Nargis and the Sichuan earthquake in China in 2008, the H1N1 pandemic in 2009, the earthquakes in Haiti and Chile in 2010 – among others that demand humanitarian aid - by exposing the vulnerability and fragility of networks, they arouse the interest of researchers from different areas such as Physics, Engineering, Computer Science, Sociology, Biology, which contribute to the advancement of studies in the humanitarian context [49]. Thus, research in logistics and supply chain, within the humanitarian context, has seen a significant increase in the amount of emerging work, mainly journal articles [34, 49, 61].

The growing impact of disasters and conflicts is putting pressure on Humanitarian Organizations (HO) to provide effective operations [30]. One factor causing inefficient responses to disaster-affected areas is the lack of coordination and collaboration among HSC actors or organizations [62]. Therefore, studies suggest that responsiveness requires

effective coordination of activities and integration of processes along the chain, as well flexibility and standardization of operations [42, 51].

As the performance of humanitarian operations largely depends on the extent of the efficiency and effectiveness of the logistics operations, several strategies are needed and studied to improve the performance and management of the supply chain [14]. Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are crucial collaborative tools in the context of Humanitarian Logistics [62]. This statement can be confirmed in several studies [4, 22, 41, 54-55].

Finally, the perception of the role of aid recipients has changed in recent decades from a passive role of victim in the supply chain to an important role, with their views incorporated into the performance assessment in HSC [28].

Answer - RQ2

Although the performance of HSC has received more attention in the current literature, its performance measurement remains a challenge [2, 18, 30, 36]. Most of the challenges in developing and implementing humanitarian performance measurement are a result of the complex operating environment, with limited capacity and motivation of humanitarian workers – often volunteers – to collect accurate data [25, 38].

However, it appears that scholars have been developing and proposing performance measurement structures based on existing models and techniques, such as the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) [18-19, 33], the SCOR [19, 29-30] and the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) [26]. Thus, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) found in the literature [5, 11, 18-19, 25, 26, 30, 34] can be divided into financial and non-financial, according to the perspectives presented in the BSC as:

Financial

- ✓ Amount of sufficient and timely fund received from institutional and private donors;
- ✓ Budgeting for operational activities;
- ✓ Deviation from project budget;
- ✓ Transportation and warehousing costs;
- ✓ SC cost (inc. personnel)/total program cost;
- ✓ Supply chain management cost;
- ✓ Total cost of distribution;
- ✓ Overhead cost;
- ✓ Percentage of unused stocks at end of project;
- ✓ Level of fundraising (income generation) and development resources;

- ✓ Warehousing cost, number of vehicles;
- ✓ Cost of distributing relief goods;
- ✓ Costs per activity.

Client/ Society

- ✓ N^o of shops owned by refugees;
- ✓ Refugees with sufficient income to meet basic needs;
- ✓ Camp inhabitants with income;
- ✓ Quality and availability of relief items;
- ✓ Speed of delivery;
- ✓ On-time reporting to donors;
- ✓ HO reputation;
- ✓ Total cargo delivered;
- ✓ Aid prioritization by item type;
- ✓ Aid prioritization by location;
- ✓ % orders not met on time;
- ✓ % orders met on time;
- ✓ % of complaints/returns;
- ✓ Delivery performance to customer commit date;
- ✓ Documentation accuracy;
- ✓ Delivery date reliability;
- ✓ Quality and availability of goods and services which are relevant to the needs;
- ✓ Number of beneficiaries helped;
- ✓ Donors' auditing;
- ✓ Access to next market;
- ✓ Inhabitants-shop-ratio;
- ✓ Hospitalinhabitants ratio;
- ✓ Neonatal mortality rate;
- ✓ Childrenschool ratio;
- ✓ Available drinking water;
- ✓ On-time delivery.

Internal Processes

- ✓ Operational cost;
- ✓ Process procurement lead-time/ benchmark;
- ✓ % Procurement request with mistakes; estimated/actual;
- ✓ Value of non “usable” supplies or assets;
- ✓ Cost to plan;
- ✓ Cost to delivery;
- ✓ Cost to manage product inventory;
- ✓ On-time reporting to donors on usage and impact of their funds;
- ✓ Response time;
- ✓ Percentage of prepositioned goods;
- ✓ Degree of warehouse management and logistics operations;
- ✓ Number of trained relief workers;
- ✓ Availability of online stock reports;
- ✓ % Procurement requests with confirmed estimated arrival date;
- ✓ Warehouse fill rate/warehouse turnover;
- ✓ % of supplies with existing pricelist;
- ✓ Delivery time and accuracy;
- ✓ Degree of warehouse and fleet utilization;

- ✓ Percentage of people engaged in dispensing aid;
- ✓ Procurement transactions using humanitarian logistics software;
- ✓ Percentage of vehicles managed with fleet management software
- ✓ Accuracy of record;

Learning and Innovation

- ✓ Degree of information sharing and cooperation;
- ✓ Degree of supply chain ICT utilization;
- ✓ Average hours spent on training staff;
- ✓ Innovative ideas on relief items;
- ✓ Staff turnover rate;
- ✓ Average hours spent on learning logistics;
- ✓ Percentage of staff with certification (or comparable) qualification;
- ✓ Number of volunteers;
- ✓ Headcount per region/country;
- ✓ Staff retention rate;
- ✓ Time per activity.

Unlike commercial organizations, HO often employs objectives that maximize some measure of service, in addition to minimizing costs [23]. Furthermore, there is a variety of HL performance situations that involve a multi-agent and multi-objective decision-making problem, covering more resources than business logistics [54]. To be effective, the measurement system and KPIs need to be adapted to each operational situation [11, 19]. However, there are few tools and insights available in the literature on how HOs can design and implement HSC performance management, essentially generating a lack of consensus among researchers on a common framework and making performance measurement in that context, quite challenging [5, 27, 36].

Answer - RQ3

Some issues that deserve further exploration are:

- ✓ Development of a decision support system (DSS) to assist humanitarian organizations;
- ✓ Use of stochastic or fuzzy approach to incorporate in DSS the variability and uncertainty of HL;
- ✓ Metaheuristics in large-scale network problems, aiming to provide objective and effective practices to build optimal and fast solutions in a real-world disaster scenario;
- ✓ Convergent studies between humanitarian and sustainability goals;
- ✓ Information management in support of decision making at all levels in organizations;
- ✓ Analyze performance objectives and their

- role in decision making;
- ✓ Evaluate the link between humanitarian supply chain (HSC) performance objectives and the organization's goal in relation to the humanitarian mission;
- ✓ Explore the impact of Cloud Computing on HSC agility;
- ✓ Compare patterns of partner relationships in order to extract more information about HO behaviors;
- ✓ Study how information reaching HL beneficiaries influences HSC performance;
- ✓ Apply in practice the theoretical models developed (case studies);
- ✓ Developing computational artifices that assist the HOs in designing, implementing and monitoring HSC performance;
- ✓ Measure the performance of humanitarian-business partnerships on HSC performance;
- ✓ Compare in more depth the applicability and advantages or disadvantages of alternative approaches to performance measurement and management;
- ✓ Investigate the adaptability, alignment, coordination, and collaboration of stakeholders in HSC dynamics.

Figure 3 summarizes the main relationships between the research questions studied.

Figure 3. Findings framework

Conclusion

In this research, the main KPIs collected in the studied literature were presented. However, to be effective, the measurement system and the KPIs need to be adapted to each operational situation, and more tools that support performance evaluation need to be explored.

We also highlight that currently the beneficiaries play an important role in the humanitarian supply chain, considering that their perception is essential to compose a performance evaluation instrument. In addition, the collection of accurate data is

indispensable for the implementation of performance evaluation, but it is hindered by the complex operational environment of the humanitarian supply chain, combined with the limitations of training of employees in the humanitarian sector.

Thus, it becomes necessary to focus on the development/improvement of performance measurement implementation and management tools in humanitarian supply chains and how to ensure the adequate availability of accurate data. To this end, the involvement of relevant stakeholders in the supply chain, especially donors, and the training of employees in the humanitarian supply chain becomes indispensable.

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